

Jamun seed derived activated carbon as an efficient adsorbent for methylene blue removal

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Abstract:

The removal of carcinogenic aqueous pollutants by using activated carbons produced from cheap and renewable precursors such as agricultural wastes has received great attention because of its low cost and high performance. Methylene blue (MB) which is one of the most commonly used cationic dye for coloring, may cause adverse effects to many forms of life [1]. In this study, we have used Jamun seed, an inexpensive biomass as a precursor to prepare activated carbon by chemical activation with KOH, followed by pyrolysis at 900°C [2]. This high surface area ($747.5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) possessed activated carbon was used for MB removal from aqueous solution. Batch adsorption studies were conducted under varying conditions of influential parameters and the maximum removal efficiency was found to be 97.77% at room temperature. Experimental data were analyzed using various isotherms and kinetic models followed by the thermodynamic study in order to understand the adsorption mechanism in detail.

Keywords: Jamun seed, Activated carbon, Methylene blue, Adsorption

References

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